

HITTING TWO BIRDS WITH ONE STONE: SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY B.COM MODEL IN CORPORATE AUDITING

Dr. P. S. Aithal* & Sonia Delrose Noronha**

* Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore, Karnataka

** B.Com Department, Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Pandeshwar,
Mangalore, Karnataka

Abstract:

The parents of many students while admitting their ward in intermediate classes and undergraduate classes dream to make them Chartered Accountants. CA is most aspired career goal of many students too. There are two entry opportunities for the aspirants to get admission. The first opportunity is soon after twelfth standard and second entry opportunity is after Graduation in any stream. Even if both entries are equally attractive, students prefer to enter to intermediate level after graduation due to the fact that graduation is very important to encash other options too in career path. Thus, CA ambitious students have the challenge to prepare their bachelor degree exams and CA intermediate exam simultaneously during their undergraduate education studies. To solve this constraint of the simultaneous study of two courses with the different curriculum, Srinivas University is starting a B.Com programme in Corporate Auditing with CA intermediate curriculum as well as B.Com syllabus. The syllabus of B.Com – Corporate auditing is developed by combining CA intermediate subjects and regular B.Com subjects with more vigor. The paper contains the details of this new B. Com programme with CA syllabus including the compulsory information technology subjects, soft skill training for competitive exams and 4 months full-time internship with the auditors. We have also discussed the special features, advantages, and benefits of the programme to earn Dual degree/certification by hitting two birds with one stone.

Index Terms: B.Com in Corporate Auditing, Curriculum of CA Intermediate & Dual Degree/Certification Through UG Course

1. Introduction:

Increasing productivity through innovation is a common practice in the modern competitive society where either improvement in existing processes, or radical changes in the processes of a system or new way of fulfilling the objective of the system are having equal importance. Productivity is not about how busy or efficient the system is but it's about how much the system has accomplished its objectives towards fulfilling its goal. Accomplishment in the workplace is the buzzword that determines one's personality. Achievements are required for one's career growth. Modern competitive world with advanced technology and social change has provided plethora of opportunities to the present generation. Winning in today's global market that offers ample of choices together with distractions is very challenging since organizations want multitasking employees. Education is the key which develops the students to face the modern organizational requirements. As one is aware education all over the world is advanced creating an environment to move ahead for the highly talented and motivated people. But cost and mainly time a student has to spend to gain knowledge and skills to suit the requirements of industry are the main factors to be considered. Innovations in higher educational system covered long way and its contribution improved the quality of education and quality of graduates [1-2]. Several studies on innovations and quality in higher education including Strategic Planning in Higher Education Institutions [3], Innovations and Best Practices can Transform Higher Education Institutions [4], quality

in higher education [5-6], Internal Quality Assurance Cell and its Contribution [7], Enhancement of Graduate attributes in Higher Education Institutions through Stage Models [8], Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions [9], Effective Leadership and Governance [10], Strategy Development and Deployment in Higher Education Institutions [11], Faculty Empowerment Strategies in Higher Education Institutions [12], Unique & Successful Model in Integrated Development [13], Applying SWOC Analysis to an Institution of Higher Education [14], Techniques for Electric Energy Auditing in Education System [15], Societal Expectation And Institutional Accountability in Higher Education [16], Methods and Approaches for Employability Skill Generation in Higher Educational Institutions [17], Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions through Best Practices in Library [18], Analysis of Academic Administrative System Implemented in Higher educational institution [19], Learning through Team Centric Exercise & Key Point Pedagogy - An effective Learning Model for Slow Learners in Higher Education Training [20], Opportunities and Challenges for Private Universities [21], Innovations in Private Universities [22], Creating Innovators through setting up organizational Vision, Mission and Core Values : a Strategic Model in Higher Education [23], Comparative Study on MBA Programmes in Private & Public Universities [24], Impact of On-line Education on Higher Education System [25], Innovations in Higher Education - A new model implemented in MCA degree programme [26], Environmental Consciousness in Higher Educational Institutions [27], Analysis of Choice Based Credit System in Higher Education [28], Innovations in Student Centric Learning – A Study of Top Business Schools [29], Innovations in Experimental Learning – A Study of World Top Business Schools [30], How to Increase Research Productivity in Higher Educational Institutions [31], Academic Support through Information System [32], and Quality Teaching and Learning as Practice Within Different Disciplinary Discourses [33], Innovative Education Model to realize Ideal Education System [34], ABCD analysis of Stage Model in Higher Education [35]) Analysis of NAAC Accreditation System using ABCD framework [36], Application of ABCD Analysis Framework on Private University System [37], The Study of New National Institutional Ranking System using ABCD Framework [38], Educational institutions quest for service quality: customers’ perspective [39], Comparative study of quality practices in higher education institutions [40], Quality in higher education-a survey [41], Blended learning: Uncovering its transformative potential in higher education [42], Innovations in Experimental Learning – A Study of World Top Business Schools [43], Academic Support through Information System [44], Changing Approaches in Campus Placements - A new futuristic Model [45], Information Technology Innovations in Library Management [46], Teaching - Learning Process in Higher Education Institutions [47], Maintaining Teacher Quality in Higher Education Institutions [48], Student performance and Learning Outcomes in Higher Education Institutions [49], Catering Student Enrollment and Retaining Diversity in Higher Education Institutions [50], Student Evaluation and Reforms in Higher Education Institutions [51] are studied and published.

Vocational education in universities is no doubt playing a role in molding the amateur students. But the accepted fact is that we are in the era that requires fast transformation. The role played by the universities in designing the purpose, pedagogy and methodologies requires a change that makes students ready for the jobs as desired by the organizations as well as pave way for individual accomplishment without wasting much time. Moreover this education should remain both affordable and accessible to all. Technology and innovation has contributed to the alternatives required

in higher education. There is a need for innovation in the higher education system so that the students are ready for globalized job market. To cope up with the arising needs the researcher has developed a dual course model in B.Com and Corporate Auditing that will help a student gain the knowledge of the commerce graduation degree, simultaneously fulfilling the requirements of CA intermediate also called C.A.(IPCC) [52]. This model attempts to make the student multi talented as well as save time before he is ready for the job market.

2. Innovations in Higher Education

John Brennan et. al. [53] in their report on “Study on innovation in higher education”, have found that the main challenges across the world faced by higher education that is leading to innovation is the pressure from globalization, the changing supply and demand for higher education and the higher education funding. They say that these challenges determine the development and implementation of various innovative practices. They opine that these challenges may trigger the introduction of different innovative practices in different institutional contexts. Innovation in higher education is a small improvement or drastic change in existing education model to add values to students learning on knowledge, skills, and experience. Table 1 lists various innovations made worldwide in higher education system to make the education as student centric.

Table 1: Innovations in Higher Education

S.No	Student Centric Innovation	Benefits	Organizations offering
1	Online Open education	It helps students from anywhere and anybody to avail education.	Online education consortiums/portals like edX, ALISON, NPTEL etc.
2	Choice Based Credit System	Students can choose the subjects as per their preference to earn required credit.	Many universities in the world
3	Competency based Credit System	Students have to earn required competency to pass a subject or degree. There is no fixed time frame to complete a course. Students may have their own pace of learning.	New innovation by some schools and colleges in developed countries
4	Continuous assessment examination system	Assessments in the form of exams are spread over the course instead of course end exam only. Students have no pressure to remember the entire semester or year curriculum during the final exam.	Autonomous institutions like business schools
5	Open book examination system	Students can refer any book or supporting materials while answering the exam. The questions are designed to apply the concepts to different problems to solve them.	Innovative autonomous institutions in developed countries. Mostly private universities.

6	Dual Degree Programmes	Students can register two courses simultaneously and get graduation in both areas. This allows them to utilize their time effectively to earn multiple degrees.	New trend started in many private universities mostly in developed countries.
7	Student Exchange Programs	Through exchange of a group of students between different cultures/social environment, students can get exposure and learn to become better decision maker.	World top business schools have adopted this feature for providing foreign exposure.
8	Semester Abroad system	Wide exposure and skill development leading to enhanced job opportunity.	New up-coming autonomous institutions in developing countries are offering this feature by collaborating with identified universities in developed countries.
9	Earn while learn model	Students get working experience, enhanced participation and responsibility in classroom, and realize the value for money.	Popular in developed countries, now spreading to developing countries.
10	Project & Research based learning	Experimental and experiential learning opportunity and creation of new knowledge.	Autonomous technical institutions and business schools are offering this scheme for industrial and research exposure.

3. Dual Degree Model: Opportunities & Challenges

Dual degree model is now becoming famous and acceptable both by educationists and students to become expert in multidisciplinary areas by utilizing their time optimally [54]. Many universities in developed countries are already providing dual degree programmes and Universities in developing countries are also following the same model as depicted in Table 2.

Table 2: Some of Dual Degree Programmes offered by Universities in Developed Countries

S.No	Dual Degrees	University/Institute	Country
1	BS & BA B.S. & B.E.	California Institute of Technology	USA
2	Dual degree P.G. Programs	University of Oxford	United Kingdom
3	P.G. Programs like M.S. & MBA, MD & MBA, MA & MBA, JD & MBA	Stanford University	USA

	MPP & MBA etc.		
4	JD & M.Phil, JD & LL.M, LL.M & MCL,	University of Cambridge	United Kingdom
5	MArch/MCP or MArch/MCP, MBA & MS in Engineering, MBA & MS, MBA & MS etc	Massachusetts Institute of Technology	USA
6	MBA & JD, MD & MBA ; MD & MPH DMD & MBA, MBA & MPP JD & MPP etc.	Harvard University	United Kingdom
7	MPA & JD MD & Ph.D.	Princeton University	USA
8	No Dual Degree Programs Available	Imperial College London	United Kingdom
9	No Dual Degree Programs Available	ETH– Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich	Switzerland
10	MBA & MPP, JD & MBA; JD & MS AM & MBA, MBA & MS	University of Chicago	USA
11	MBA & MS ; MBA & MA, MBA & JD ; MBA & MPH, MD & MBA ; MD & MPH, MSW & MPH ; JD & MPH LL.M & MPH ;	Johns Hopkins University	USA
12	JD & MBA ; JD & MA, MBA & MARCH, MBA & MD, MBA & MPH, MBA & MA, MBA & MEM, MBA & MFA, MSN & MPH, MD & MPH, MA & MPH, MD & JD Etc.	Yale University	USA
13	JD & MBA, MBA & MPH, MBA & MA, MD & MS, U.G. Dual Degree Programs	University of California, Berkeley	USA
14	U.G. BA Dual Degree MA & M.Sc.	University College London	United Kingdom
15	MBA & MA, MBA & MSW, MBA & MD, MBA & DDS, MBA & JD, MBA & MPH, MBA & MIA, MBA & M.Arch. MBA & MSN. MA & M.Sc. MA & MS Etc. Five Years Integrated Course.	Columbia University	USA
16	MPP & JD, MPP & MBA, MPP & MD, MPP & MPH, MPP & MSW, MPH & MBA, MPH & MD, MPH & JD, MBA & MA etc.	University of California, Los Angeles	USA
17	U.G. Dual Degree Programs P.G. Dual Degree Programs	University of Pennsylvania	USA
18	MBA & JD, MBA & M.Engg, MBA & MD, MPS & MBA, MBA & MHA, MBA & MILR, JD & MPA, and other combinations. Five Years Integrated Course	Cornell University	USA
19	JD & MBA, PharmD & MBA,	University of Toronto	Canada

	MGA & MBA Five Years Integrated Course		
20	JD & LLM, JD & MBA, JD & MA JD & MD, JD & MPP, JD & MS MD & MBA, MPP & MBA etc.	Duke University	USA
21	U.G. Dual Degree Programs P.G. Dual Degree Programs	University of Michigan	USA
22	P.G. Dual Degree Programs	Carnegie Mellon University	USA
23	P.G. Dual Degree Programs	London School of Economics and Political Science	United Kingdom
24	U.G. Joint Degree Programs P.G. Joint Degree Programs	University of Edinburgh	United Kingdom
25	U.G. Dual Degree Programs P.G. Dual Degree Programs	Northwestern University	USA
26	U.G. Dual Degree Programs P.G. Dual Degree Programs Five Years Integrated Course Double MBA programs	National University of Singapore	Singapore
27	U.G. Dual Degree Programs P.G. Dual Degree Programs Five Years Integrated Course	King's College London	United Kingdom
28	No Dual Degree Programs Available	Karolinska Institute	Sweden
29	No Dual Degree Programs Available	LMU Munich	Germany
30	MBA & MFA, JD & LLM, JD & MA, JD & MBA, JD & MSW, JD & MPA, BS & BS, BS & BA,	New York University	USA

Table 3: Some of Dual Degree Programmes offered by Indian Universities

S.No	Dual Degrees	No. of Years	University/Institute & State
1	P.G. Programs in Engineering & Management, U.G. in Hotel Management & PG in Management	5 Years	Manipal University Manipal, Karnataka
2	Integrated B.Tech + MBA	5 Years	NIIT University, Rajasthan JK Lakshmipat University, Rajasthan Amity University, Noida Lingaya's University, Faridabad Indraprastha University, Delhi IIT, Delhi etc.
3	B.Pharm & MBA	5 Years	Jaipur University
4	B.Pharm & M.Pharm	5 Years	IIT, Kharagpur IIT, Kanpur

5	BBA & LLB	5 Years	Alliance University, Karnataka state law university, Christ University, Reva University, Amity University, Geonka University
7	B.Tech. & MBA	5 Years	Amity University JNTU, Hyderabad Punjab University Delhi Technological University
8	M.Sc. & Ph.D.	5 Years	IIT, Bombay IIT, Chennai
9	MBA & Ph.D.	5 Years	IIIT, Allahabad
10	M.Tech. & Ph.D.	5 Years	IIT, Guwahati
10	B.Tech & MS, M.Tech & MS, MBA & MPH, MBA & MHM, MBA & MS(IT)	5 Years 2 Years	SRM University IIT, Hyderabad
11	B.Tech. & M.Tech.	5 Years	IIT Delhi IIT Kanpur etc.
12	BBA & MBA	5 Years	Nirma University
13	BCA & MCA	5 Years	Srinivas University, Mangalore Jain University, Bangalore

Advantages of Dual Degree Programmes:

- ✓ To lessen the pressure on graduates becoming unemployable in the market, the integrated programmes are designed to help students become job-ready.
- ✓ It's a unique opportunity for students to pursue simultaneously two or more degrees/diploma programmes without break.
- ✓ Some companies look for both engineering and managerial skills and find dual graduates handy. The job readiness is much higher than regular degrees.
- ✓ Time saving: The students desire to do two courses can save time in terms of years by doing dual degree programmers.
- ✓ Opportunity to increase knowledge and skills in multi-disciplinary areas depending on self interest.

4. Developing Curriculum to Meet Challenges:

With the liberalization of commerce and management education since 1990s, one can notice the unprecedented growth in the number of management and commerce institutions over a few years both by government and private players. New era of globalization has brought in a lot of opportunities and challenges. To meet these requirements confidently the existing traditional commerce education seems to be irrelevant. Though the students have a wide choice in institutions the present curriculum as per the changing environment requires immediate changes. Restructuring the existing business education system to meet the future challenges of the economic, manufacturing and service sectors seems to be the need of the hour. The students should have a varied choice regarding the subjects in which they want to study

and accordingly they can develop their skills and equip themselves for the future and ultimately make themselves competitive for the future needs of changes in both in the industrial and services sectors in India and abroad. B.Com. graduates have immense career prospects in the form of Accountants, Tax Consultants, Human Resource Managers, Bankers, BPO/KPO Jobs, Auditors, Stock Brokers, Lecturers, Finance Consultants, Insurance Consultants, Government Jobs, Market Researchers, Entrepreneurs, Administrative Jobs and civil service jobs [55-56]. B.Com. graduates can also aspire for higher education like M.Com., MBA, Chartered Accountants (CA) / Cost and Work, Accountants (CWA) / Company Secretary (CS).

5. Essentiality of Graduation Degree along with ICAI Associate Membership:

As per the revised scheme of education and training for chartered Accountancy course the students who wish to take entry to CA (IPCC) course has to be a graduate or Post Graduate in any discipline (Marks required minimum 55% for commerce graduate/post graduate and minimum of 60% for other graduate/ Post graduate) or intermediate level passed student of Institute of company secretaries of India and Institute of cost Accountants of India.

6. Innovation in Dual Degree – CA Intermediate Course (IPCC) & B.Com. in Corporate Auditing :

To understand the innovations required separate details of B.Com. curriculum (Table 4) offered and CA intermediate (IPCC) curriculum (Table 5) are given below. Further the newly developed dual degree B.Com in corporate Auditing is shown in Table 6. One can see that the dual degree B.Com in corporate Auditing is a combination of two degrees offering a plethora of subjects to students. Students who complete Bachelors of Commerce gain the knowledge in the following subjects as given in table 4.

Table 4: Bachelor of Commerce (B.Com.) Subjects

I SEMESTER	II SEMESTER
1. Language I 2. Language II 3. Business Economics 4. Financial Accounting I 5. Principles of Management 6. Business Statistics and Management I 7. Constitution of India 8. Extra Curricular Activities	1. Language I 2. Language II 3. Money and Public Finance 4. Financial Accounting II 5. Modern Banking 6. Business Statistics and Management II 7. General studies (Human Rights & Gender Equity) 8. Extra Curricular Activities
III SEMESTER	IV SEMESTER
1. Language I 2. Language II 3. International trade and Finance I 4. Financial Accounting III 5. Cost and Management Accounting I 6. Elective Paper I 7. Extra Curricular Activities	1. Language I 2. Language II 3. International trade and Finance II 4. Financial Accounting IV 5. Cost and Management Accounting II 6. Elective Paper II 7. Extra Curricular Activities
V SEMESTER	VI SEMESTER
1. Business Law 2. Modern Marketing 3. Financial Management I 4. Financial Accounting V 5. Cost and Management Accounting III	1. Indian corporate Law 2. Auditing 3. Financial Management II 4. Financial Accounting VI 5. Cost and Management Accounting IV

6. Elective Paper III	6. Elective Paper II
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Elective Papers:

- ✓ Human Resource Management
- ✓ Business Taxation
- ✓ Insurance
- ✓ Advanced Banking
- ✓ Computer Application

Table 5: CA course structure and subjects for CA Intermediate Course (IPCC)

SUBJECTS	ALLOCATION OF MARKS	
GROUP 1:		
Paper 1: Accounting (100 marks)	FULL PAPER	
Paper 2: Corporate Laws & other Laws (100 marks)	Part I : Corporate Laws (60 marks)	Part – II : Other Laws (40 Marks)
Paper 3 : Cost Accounting(100 marks)	FULL PAPER	
Paper 4 : Direct Tax Laws & Indirect Tax laws (100marks)	Part – I : Direct Tax Laws (60 marks)	Part – II : Indirect Tax laws (40 marks)
GROUP – II:		
Paper 5 : Advanced Accounting (100marks)	FULL PAPER	
Paper 6 : Auditing and Assurance (100marks)	FULL PAPER	
Paper 7: Financial Management & Business Economic Environment (100 marks)	Part I :Financial Management (60 marks)	Business Economic Environment (40 marks)
Paper 8: Information Technology & Strategic Management (100 marks)	Information technology (60 marks)	Strategic Management (40 marks)

B.Com programme is designed in Corporate Auditing with CA intermediate (IPCC) curriculum. This curriculum is designed in a manner that it includes the subjects of B.Com as well as the subjects required in CA intermediate increasing the skills of the students and opportunity to register for both exams to get dual certificates by studying an integrated curriculum.

Table 6:B.Com (Corporate Auditing) Programme Structure

I SEMESTER	II SEMESTER
1. Communicative English I	1. Communicative English I
2. Communicative Hindi I	2. Communicative Hindi II
3. Business Economics	3. Modern Marketing
4. Accounting I	4.Accounting II
5. Communication and Soft Skills	5. Cost and Management Accounting I
6. Principles of Management	6. Business Statistics and Mathematics
7. Money and Public Finance	7. Direct Taxes I
8. Constitution of India, Human Rights and gender Equity	8. Information Technology and E-Commerce
III SEMESTER	IV SEMESTER

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Auditing and Assurance I 2. Direct II 3. Financial Management I 4. Cost and Management Accounting II 5. Advanced Accounting I 6. International Trade and Finance 7. IT advanced 8. Business Environment 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Auditing and Assurance II 2. Indirect Taxes 3. Financial Management II 4. Cost and Management Accounting III 5. Advanced Accounting II 6. Business Law 7. Elective Paper I 8. Corporate Law I
V SEMESTER	VI SEMESTER
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Corporate Law I I 2. Advanced Auditing 3. Financial Reporting 4. Strategic Management 5. Financial Services 6. Elective Paper III 7. Modern Banking 8. Project I 	<p>Additional soft skill development paper for competitive exams</p> <hr/> <p>Four months Practical Auditing Training with a Chartered Accountant followed by Report and Viva.</p>

Elective Papers: Any one of the papers stated below may be selected by the student to be studied in the fourth and fifth semesters as Elective paper I and Elective paper II

- ✓ Advanced Banking and Corporate Ethics
- ✓ Insurance
- ✓ Investment Management
- ✓ Human Resource Management

7. Details of the Programme:

With the globalization of Business, the size of the business entities have grown to gigantic levels increasing the gap between the Owner (share holder) and the Executive (board of directors). Governments have become stricter with new Laws and Regulations to protect the environment and mankind from the clutches of these gigantic business entities. This situation required a breed of well informed and trained auditors. The Institute of Chartered Accountants of India (ICAI) to take care of the requirement, the requirement for the well informed and trained people is increasing. In this environment, the objective of the degree program B.Com. (Corporate Auditing) of Srinivas University is to bring out such graduates who are well informed and trained in the same lines of the curriculum prescribed by the ICAI and to enable them, if they are interested, to pursue CA course and complete without any problem. The main objective of the Bachelor Degree Program of Srinivas University is:

- ✓ To lay a strong foundation of the communicative languages, core and current subjects of the discipline the students opt along with the mandatory allied subjects and the extra learning they require.
- ✓ To enable the students to face the global challenges with their all round knowledge.
- ✓ To enable the students to imbibe the research and innovative aptitude.
- ✓ To make the students practical in their life.

Eligibility:

A candidate who has passed the two years Pre-University Examination conducted by the Pre-University Education Board in the State of Karnataka or any other 10+2 examination considered as equivalent thereto by Srinivas University is eligible for admission to these programs.

Figure 1: Various components of B.Com. -CA (IPCC) Integrated Model

Examination:

Examination is conducted at the end of each semester. Results will be declared within ten days of the last subject examination of the semester.

8. Analysis of Dual Course Model:

After a thorough market analysis and the requirement of the market it was observed that there is a need to develop students with more diversified skills. Competition had made organizations more demanding. One has to market himself to get a job. Moreover sustaining back in the organization is possible only when one has gained the required knowledge and skills. Further Chartered Accountancy is considered to be a profession that defines the creamy layer of the society. Though it is a dream of every commerce aspirant, fulfilling it has a route to be followed as prescribed by the professional body. Considering the above personal, industrial requirements this model provides a scope for students to fulfill their dreams. The B.Com. in corporate auditing is an integrated model which contains many components as shown in fig. 1. In addition to training on CA (IPCC) course, these components include Communication language proficiency, Knowledge on Indian constitution, Proficiency in business mathematics and statistics, Knowledge on banking and insurance, Skills on e-commerce, Company law, Proficiency in economics and Marketing strategy, and Experience on doing an auditing project. These eight major components of B.Com. in corporate auditing make it an Innovative Integrated Model.

Special Features:

- ✓ The B.Com (Corporate Auditing) degree program is structured on the Credit Based Semester Scheme in conformity with the UGC guidelines.

- ✓ The curriculum is prepared keeping in view that the student who is studying this B.Com. degree program shall be able to complete Chartered Accountancy Course of the Institute of Chartered Accountants of India with full self confidence.
- ✓ The curriculum is practical oriented taking into consideration the industry requirement.
- ✓ The curriculum is designed such that even though the student is not interested in pursuing Chartered Accountancy Course, he shall become a highly competent Corporate Auditor/Advisor.
- ✓ The students are required to take part in co-curricular and extra-curricular activities and their participation is compulsory.
- ✓ At the end of each even semester, the student has to undergo a pre-determined/self study project and submit his report which enhances his practical knowledge.
- ✓ The entire final semester is a industry attached project/training with a practicing Chartered Accountant culminating in a Report evaluated through Viva.

9. ABCD Analysis of the Programme:

Any innovative concept or business model can be analysed using either SWOC, or newly developed ABCD analysis method. ABCD listing and ABCD framework are two models of qualitative [57-58] and quantitative ABCD analysis method [59-61] respectively. In this section, we have used ABCD analysis for qualitative listing of advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages of dual degree model.

Advantages:

- ✓ B.Com in Corporate Auditing course is a combination of B.Com and C.A intermediate course syllabus that give graduates the advantage to be competitive in a rapidly changing work environment both in India and abroad.
- ✓ With extra study in comparison to a single course and additional effort both by teaching experts and the students, one has the advantage of gaining knowledge of two degrees.
- ✓ Students can save time and money and master the combination of two disciplines.
- ✓ Students will be trained in two disciplines, widening the career opportunities and increasing the chances of getting a job in varied disciplines and making the way to pursue CA easily.
- ✓ B.Com. –CA (IPCC) Integrated Model has value additions like Communication skills, e-commerce skills, Banking and Insurance, proficiency in Business Mathematics and Statistics, and networking opportunity with B.Com. classmates.

Benefits:

- ✓ Curriculum benefit: A student who has joined B.Com. course studies C.A. intermediate course syllabus so that he can easily pass C.A. exam without additional effort.
- ✓ Time benefit: A student who has joined B.Com. course studies C.A. intermediate course syllabus so that he can easily pass C.A. exam without spending additional time.
- ✓ Benefit to do Graduation Degree: C.A. aspirants who focus on CA intermediate exam loose opportunity to complete their graduation degree. By means of studying both simultaneously, a student can get graduation as well as article ship together.

- ✓ Based on this model, after completing B.Com. (corporate auditing) and C.A.(IPCC), a student can do CA (final) and M.Com.((corporate auditing) simultaneously.
- ✓ B.Com. –CA (IPCC) Integrated Model provides additional knowledge and skills compared to students studying only C.A,(IPCC) which gives more confidence to the students in their future career.
- ✓ Alternative Career: If any student fails to pass C.A. (IPCC) or C.A. (Final), he can take alternative path of B.Com. and M.Com. in Corporate auditing and get a decent job in the society.

Constraints:

- ✓ Programme cost: Taking two courses certainly increases the exam fee cost.
- ✓ Additional effort: Even though the two courses have same curriculum, students have to take two exams to get the benefits of two courses.

Disadvantages:

- ✓ Longer path: C.A. intermediate has two entry schemes with direct entry soon after 12th standard through C.A.-CPT and second entry is after a graduation degree. Thus second path is a longer path which need graduation degree to take C.A. (IPCC) exam.
- ✓ Diverted Attention: The eligibility condition to take C.A.(IPCC) is graduation degree, usually, the students focus is diverted to involve in additional co-curricular and extra-curricular activities compared to direct entry after 12th standard.

10. Conclusion:

The model of higher education can be improved by means of adding new values at various stages so that the students should get advantages in the form of enhanced knowledge, skills or improved career opportunities. One of such innovation is proposed in this paper where a student on the completion of three years undergraduate programme of B.Com. degree in Corporate Auditing, can take C.A. (IPCC) exam confidently due to the study of same syllabus in B,Com. course. With a graduation degree, they will be ready to face the challenges of the job market as well as to attempt the better career opportunity by completing C.A. (IPCC). This integrated model will help students to earn dual degree/certification by hitting two birds using one stone.

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